
112. Our Galaxy's central bar

BARS are rectangular or 'boxy' morphological stellar structures, present in the centres of some 50–70% of spiral galaxies, and 25–30% of all galaxies. They vary in prominence, from those dominating the disk's appearance, to weak distortions verging on the subjective. They often appear more pronounced in infrared images.

The fraction of galaxies with bars is known to depend on factors such as environment, mass, and gas content. And the bar fraction appears to evolve with redshift, with a lower overall rate at higher redshifts.

While it has long been suspected that our own spiral Milky Way galaxy is 'barred' (Johnson, 1957), its structure, its size and orientation, and its 'pattern speed' (the rotation of the bar feature, rather than the constituent stars), are still subject to debate. This is mainly because, from our edge-on location within the disk, its defining non-axisymmetric structure cannot easily be seen. Dust opacity further complicates discerning its morphology.

Observational probes have therefore used the kinematics of H I and H₂ gas in the inner regions, star counts (e.g. red clump giants), and gravitational microlensing.

Bars are important drivers of galaxy evolution, affecting the distribution of angular momentum, interacting with the stellar disk, the dark matter halo, and gas transport, and influencing star formation.

BARS, and indeed spiral arms, arise as inevitable consequences of stellar orbits. Early insights into their origin and dynamics (e.g. Lindblad, 1956; Kalnajs, 1973) was reviewed by Toomre (1977).

Their formation and evolution is just one part of the hugely complex dynamical processes that occur within the vast stellar systems that comprise a galaxy. Their origin and properties emerge from detailed numerical descriptions of stellar orbits within a (rotating) asymmetric gravitational potential (e.g. Kormendy 2013).

Because the mass in galaxies is distributed in radius, and not all at one central point (i.e. their gravitational potential is non-Keplerian), the general orbit of a disk star is a rosette, rather than a closed ellipse. Superposed on their azimuthal rotation are radial oscillations at the 'epicycle frequency', determined by the disk properties.

THREE PRINCIPAL orbital resonances are then key to understanding bars (and spirals): the corotation resonance, and the inner and the outer Lindblad resonances. The former occurs at the radius where the star's velocity around the galaxy is equal to that of the rotating potential. The inner Lindblad resonance occurs where the rotating star 'overtakes' the potential, encountering its peak at the epicycle frequency. The outer Lindblad resonance, conversely, occurs where the potential overtakes the more slowly rotating star.

It turns out that if closed inner Lindblad resonance orbits produce a trailing enhancement in density, of either spiral or bar-like form, the orbits will precess together, preserving the spiral or bar shape.

Beyond this simple picture are many complications, including the effects of spiral arms and galaxy interactions. And the understanding of bars has evolved as **numerical simulations** and observations of other galaxies have improved (e.g. Combes et al., 1990; Combes 2011). For example, in the absence of a dark matter halo, a thin stellar disk is dynamically unstable, causing it to buckle and collapse, forming a stellar bar in the process. That not all galaxies have bars was considered as early evidence that galaxy disks must be embedded in massive halos.

THE ROBUST formation and persistence of bars is also confirmed in the most recent cosmological simulations, such as Illustris/TNG (Pillepich et al., 2018), NewHorizon (Dubois et al., 2021) and EAGLE (Cavanagh et al., 2022). But they generate a large variation in predicted bar fractions, ranging from 5–55%, reflecting the challenge of modelling the physical processes governing the formation and evolution of galaxies. And bars are confirmed to have already formed at high-redshifts, $z > 2$, as seen in recent JWST images (Guo et al., 2022).

WHILE emphasising the difficulties in separating the bar from the bulge, the inner disk and inner halo, and the further complication of a ‘super-thin’ contribution, Bland-Hawthorn & Gerhard (2016) gave its parameters as: *stellar* mass ($7 \pm 1 \times 10^9 M_\odot$), Galactic orientation ($28 - 33^\circ$), half-length (5.0 ± 0.2 kpc), scale height (180 pc), and an age of order 6–7 Gyr. Its pattern speed ($43 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$) and corresponding corotation radius (4.5–7 kpc), derived mainly from numerical and hydrodynamical simulations, remain poorly determined. The bar and bulge projections shown here were derived from near-infrared star counts by Wegg et al. (2015).

ALTHOUGH BARS are largely physically confined to regions of the galaxy within the corotation resonance, their dynamical influence may extend to the outer parts through other resonant effects. Specifically, asymmetries in the potential can impart unexpected signatures in the velocity distribution in the solar neighbourhood.

The story here becomes intricately linked with certain local anomalous stellar ‘streams’, notably the Hercules stream. Hipparcos contributed new velocities in the solar neighbourhood, from which simulations confirmed the local dynamical influence of the bar (e.g. Rabout et al., 1998; Dehnen, 1999; Dehnen, 2000; Mühlbauer & Dehnen, 2003). Dehnen (1999) estimated the bar’s pattern speed as $53 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$.

GIVEN THE TOPIC’S complexity, I can give here only a flavour of the results being enabled by Gaia.

Firstly, the combination of radial velocities and spectroscopy from APOGEE, with distances and proper motions from Gaia, has revealed the barred structure of the inner Milky Way in unprecedented detail.

Bovey et al. (2019) used APOGEE DR16 with Gaia DR2, while Leung et al. (2023) updated the analysis using APOGEE DR17 with Gaia EDR3. Combined with their determination of the distance to the Galactic centre (essay #111), their maps display the minimum in rotational velocity, and the quadrupole signature in radial velocity, expected for stars orbiting in a bar (the same feature was reported in the Gaia DR3 data by Drimmel et al., 2022).

From N-body simulations, they estimated a pattern speed of $40.1 \pm 1.8 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$, and inferred that the bar first formed ~ 8 Gyr ago. At that epoch, the decreasing turbulence of the gas disk allowed a thin disk to form, which quickly became subject to the bar instability.

THE DYNAMICS of the inner Galaxy contains important evidence for untangling the evolutionary history of the Milky Way. But the inner Galaxy’s gravitational potential is poorly constrained, in part because the length of the Galactic bar is uncertain, with half-length estimates ranging from 3.5–5 kpc. Lucey et al. (2022) used 210 000 stars from APOGEE DR17 and Gaia EDR3 to model the stellar orbits as a function of assumed potential. Their results indicate a dynamical bar length of 3.4–3.9 kpc, and a pattern speed of $39 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$.

THE OUTER DISK of the Milky Way offers another possibility for exploring the dynamics and past history of the Galaxy. Because of the lower gravitational potential, imprints of perturbations in these outer regions are long-lived, resulting in them still being observable today.

Drimmel et al. (2023) used Gaia DR3 data to identify a resonant-like feature in the angular momentum distribution of young classical Cepheids (also evident in a much larger sample of red giant stars) which may also be related to the influence of the central bar.

FINALLY, two studies making use of the large-scale astrometry and photometry from Gaia DR2 have led to a remarkable result which illustrates both the accuracy and fidelity of the Gaia data, while providing further circumstantial evidence for the dark matter halo.

Chiba et al. (2021a) showed that the local stellar kinematics imply that the bar is *decelerating*, consistent with the effects of dynamical friction of a dark matter halo. As the bar slows, its resonances sweep through phase space, dragging along a portion of previously free orbits. This leads to certain multiple resonances clearly seen in the Gaia data and, in particular, reproducing the details of the Hercules stream in the local radial-azimuthal velocity plane. They derived a current slowing rate of the bar of $-4.5 \pm 1.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$ per Gyr.

Chiba et al. (2021b) used Gaia photometry to estimate metallicities, and showed that the bar’s deceleration also results in a variation of metallicity with distance from the resonance centre. Applied to solar neighbourhood stars, this provides a new and precise measure of its *current* pattern speed, $35.5 \pm 0.8 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$ (placing the corotation radius at 6.6 ± 0.2 kpc). And with this pattern speed, the corotation resonance precisely explains the kinematics of the Hercules stream. The bar’s deceleration, $\sim 24\%$ since formation, transfers angular momentum to the halo by dynamical friction, in the process reinforcing the existence of a standard dark-matter halo (rather than alternative models of gravity).

WITH EACH data release, Gaia is revealing much new structure in the phase space of stars. Many new insights into our Galaxy’s bar, its resonances, and its relationship with the spiral arms and our Galaxy’s dark matter halo, can be expected over the coming decade.